

ENHANCED COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL THICK SECTION THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY FIBER HYBRIDIZATION

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ABSTRACT

With the success of composite materials in high performance structures new, structural applications are being identified for use of thicker section composites. New thermoplastic matrix composites are being considered for many applications. In this study, unidirectional thick section (16 and 40 plies) hybrid polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) matrix composite compressive response was evaluated. The hybridization of composites was achieved with E-glass and AS4-graphite fibers. A symmetric sandwich configuration consisting of exterior E-glass fibers and AS4-graphite in the core was used to enhance the mechanical properties by suppressing and altering the failure modes of AS4-graphite PPS. Hybrid composites of five different AS4-graphite volume fractions (100%, 75%, 50%, 25% and 0%) were evaluated and analyzed for compressive response. The compressive strength of unidirectional E-glass and AS4-graphite PPS are 456 and 495 MPa as compared to 524.1 MPa of the hybrid 75% AS4-graphite / 25% E-glass PPS composite. Experimental results showed a distinct failure strain enhancement of hybrid composites of 20 - 65% over pure AS4-graphite PPS composites. The failure strain enhancements for the compressive response translated into higher compressive strengths of the composites. Maximum strengths were achieved for 75% AS4-graphite / 25% E-glass PPS hybrid composites. The hybrid effect is attributed to transverse support and crack arresting properties of the E-glass fibers and was quantified by measuring the increase in the failure strains of the hybrid composites as compared to that of 100% AS4-graphite PPS composites. The hybridization of the composites showed change in fracture modes from AS4-graphite composites and confirmed the crack arresting properties of the E-glass PPS. The development of the hybrid composites has demonstrated that optimum tailoring of composite structures results in compressive property enhancement as a result of appropriate fiber selection, geometry and placement.

KEY WORDS: Compressive; Fiber / Glass; Fiber / Graphite; Hybrid; Thick Laminate

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have found widespread use in the automotive, aerospace, construction and marine industry due to their excellent specific properties, improved corrosion resistance, toughness and superior fatigue properties. There is a growing interest in thick section continuous fiber reinforced composites for structural applications e.g. transportation and maritime structures [1,2]. The large hydrostatic pressures experienced by submersible structures make the compression response of thick section composites critical. Lately new high temperature thermoplastics (e.g. PEEK, PPS, J2) have been considered as matrix material in composites due to their improved toughness and better environmental resistance. Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS), a semi-crystalline thermoplastic with a glass transition temperature of 85°C and a melting temperature of 285°C was selected as matrix for the present research [3]. A sandwich hybrid configuration was utilized with E-glass exterior fibers and AS4-graphite in the core of the composite (Figure 1). To study the effect of hybridization,

unidirectional composites with five different ratios of AS4-graphite / E-glass amounts (1/0, 3/1, 1/1, 1/3 and 0/1) were evaluated. The effect on properties due to variation of thickness was studied by using composites of 16 (2.5 mm) and 40 (6.25 mm) ply thick. The fractured surfaces were observed using optical and scanning electron microscope to understand microstructure - property correlation as a function of fiber type ratio, thickness and the fiber orientation.

1.1 Compression Response The compressive response of fiber reinforced composites is one of the least understood composite topics. The compressive property of composite is influenced at the specimen level (e.g. specimen size, geometry, test fixture, method of loading), at macroscopic level (interlaminar distances, stacking sequence of lamina) and microscopic level (e.g., fiber - matrix interface, defects, fiber misorientation and inhomogeneities) [4,5]. These factors result in premature and complex failure modes, e.g. Euler buckling, transverse tension, fiber kinking, matrix failure or delamination. In addition the compressive strength of graphite fibers can be 33 - 50% of the tensile strength. As a result, a structure may be design limited by the compressive properties of the composite. The compression strength of fibrous composite is also affected by the test technique and the fixture used. Abdallah [6] has discussed the various available compression testing techniques.

The failure mode of continuous fiber reinforced composites in compression is influenced by material and structural factors. At structural level the specimen may fail by global or Euler buckling of the compression specimen. The critical stress required to ensure buckling of laminated composite is lower due to poor transverse properties, long aspect ratio of unsupported fibers coupled with lower compressive fiber strengths versus tension. The critical load per unit width required for buckling of laminated beams has been derived Whitney [7] to be,

$$P = E_x^b h^3 \pi^2 / 3l^2 \quad (1)$$

where E_x^b is the bending modulus of the laminate, h the thickness and l the length of the buckling section. In principle, Euler buckling may be avoided by having a short gage length. However, a short gage length may result in non-uniform stress state within the specimen. The gage length should be enough to ensure a uniform stress across the sample, and failure in the gage section.

At the microstructural level, the composite failure is affected by the local defects, inhomogeneities, fiber matrix interface, matrix strength and modulus [4,5]. The failure mode is influenced by mechanical properties of matrix and the fibers. The failure may be of the form of fiber micro-buckling, kinking, transverse deformation and fiber-matrix debonding. One of the earlier theory, to predict the compression strength of fiber reinforced composite was proposed by Rosen [8] for two dimensional reinforcement. His model assumes that the compressive failure is due to the instability of the fibers in matrix which results in micro-buckling. The fibers can buckle either out of phase i.e. extensional mode for low volume fractions of fiber (i.e. < 0.2) or in phase (shear mode) for high volume reinforcement of fibers. Rosen's expression for strength of a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite are:

$$\text{Extensional mode: } \sigma = 2 [V_f E_m E_f / 3(1 - V_f)]^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Shear Mode: } \sigma = 2 [G_m / (1 - V_f)] \quad (3)$$

E_m and E_f are the elastic moduli of fiber and matrix, G_m the shear modulus of matrix and V_f the volume fraction of fiber in the composite. For shear failure, it should be noticed that the strength is a function of only matrix properties and not of fiber properties.

Compressive properties of hybrid composite have not been studied as extensively as the tensile, flexure or the impact behavior. Kalnín [9] has observed a marked increase in the compressive modulus over rule of mixture predictions on small addition of carbon fibers to the glass reinforced composites. The increased modulus was observed only up to 15% carbon fiber content, after which the modulus decreased progressively. Piggot and Harris [10] have studied the compressive behavior of glass-carbon-Kevlar[®] 49 fiber reinforced hybrid composites. Based on his study, Piggot [11] proposed a theory for the compressive strength prediction of hybrid composites based on rule of mixtures. He obtained the following expression for the

strength of hybrid composite:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_{fmaxhi} (V_{fhi} + V_{flo}E_{flo} / E_{fhi} + V_m E_m / E_{fhi}) \quad (4)$$

σ_c is the ultimate compression strength, V_{fhi} and σ_{fmaxhi} , the volume fraction and stress in the high modulus fiber at failure, V_{flo} and V_m the volume fractions for low modulus fibers and the matrix material, E_{flo} , E_{fhi} and E_m the elastic moduli for low and high modulus fibers and the matrix material. The above equation predicted a large hybrid effect (100 - 150%). Piggot attributed the high strength of the composites to better transverse support of the low modulus fibers. This delays the buckling of higher modulus fibers and enhances the compressive strength of the composite. The compression response of thick section composites has not been extensively studied. Camponeschi [12] and Clark and Lisagor [13] have conducted analysis of the compressive response of thick section composites. Camponeschi recommended use of end loaded fixtures, with samples of varying thickness, widths and slenderness ratios to be tested.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Composite Processing The composites were processed in a microprocessor controlled Lipton autoclave. The AS4-graphite and E-glass PPS prepreg tapes were joined together into lamina of 300 mm by 225 mm. The plies were bonded lightly to prevent any change of orientation during handling and processing activities. The assembly was vacuum bagged in a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) film, placed in an autoclave and evacuated, and heated to 315°C in 45 minutes. At 315°C, a pressure of 1.05 MPa was applied using commercial nitrogen for 10 minutes. The composite was cooled to 176°C (below the crystallization temperature of PPS, 221°C) in 25 minutes with the pressure was maintained at 1.05 MPa. The composite was further cooled to room temperature in 20 minutes. Simultaneously, the pressure was also reduced to the atmospheric pressure.

2.2 Compression Evaluation The compression testing fixture was designed after a careful survey of the existing literature [4]. Use of a shear loaded compression test fixture would have resulted in a shear failure at the adhesive joints near the tabs or in the composite. It should be mentioned that a shear loaded fixture e.g. IITRI is preferable to the end loaded fixture for 2.5 mm thick composite samples. However to maintain the consistency of the tests, all samples were tested in the end loaded fixture. Thickness variation of the samples coupled with high compressive loads required for failure, precluded utilization of shear loaded IITRI / Celanese compressive fixtures. Hence it was decided to use an end-loaded compression test fixture (Figure 2 a). The fixture consists of two steel end blocks. The sample ends are secured in the steel blocks with the aid of 12.5 mm thick steel pieces. The steel blocks constrain the specimen ends and prevent the composite ends from brooming. The specimen alignment is assured by using 6.25 mm thick alignment pins. Figure 2 b shows a compression test sample. The samples are 101 mm long. Each end of the sample was tabbed with cross-ply glass epoxy tabs. Some of the samples were instrumented with the Micromeritics strain gages to measure the failure strain and the elastic modulus of the composites. The composites were loaded with a constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/minute. The fractured specimen were examined to study the different failure initiation and propagation modes. Some of the tests were stopped at about 80% of the failure loads to examine the samples for damage development prior to failure. The specimen were polished and examined using a Zeiss Model ICM 405 optical microscope and a JEOL JSM-35CF Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effect of Hybridization on Compressive Failure Properties The average compressive properties of 0° orientation hybrid composites of different volume fractions are tabulated in Table I for 16 and 40 ply composites respectively. The failure strengths for the 40 ply unidirectional composites are 312.3 MPa and 346.1 MPa for E-glass and AS4-graphite PPS respectively. The hybridization of composites results in a strength enhancement, e.g. 382 MPa for 25% AS4-graphite / 75% E-glass and 420.7 MPa for 75% AS4-graphite / 25% E-glass PPS reinforcement. The 40 ply composites also show strength enhancement upon hybridization. The strength of the unidirectional E-glass and AS4-graphite PPS are 456.0 MPa and 495 MPa as compared to 524.1 MPa of the 75% AS4-graphite / E-glass PPS hybrid composite. Along with the strengths, the failure strains of the composites are also listed in the Table I. The failure strains increase with increasing E-glass content in the hybrid composite. The 16 ply composites

failed at lower elongations than the 40 ply composites due to Euler buckling. The variation of ultimate compressive strength with fraction E-glass PPS is graphically illustrated in Figures 3 (a, b) for the hybrid composites for 16 and 40 ply composite specimen. The figures also show the theoretical ultimate compressive strength of the composite calculated by two different approaches. The iso-strain approach [14] assumes that the hybrid composites fail at the failure strain of unidirectional AS4-graphite fiber, i.e. 0.34% for 16 ply and 0.44% for the 40 ply thick composites (equation 4). A second approach, the strain - transfer based on weighted average of the strength of the constituents or the rule of mixture was used for predicting the strength of the composite. This assumes that the composite failure strain is higher than the lowest failing constituent, i.e. AS4-graphite PPS. In addition to the iso-strain and strain transfer approaches, Figure 3 b also shows the predicted loads required for buckling of 16 ply composites as obtained by Equation 1.

The 40 ply composites have a slightly lower compressive modulus than the 16 ply composite. However the differences are not large as those for failure strength and strains. For example the elastic moduli for the unidirectional 16 ply composites range from 39.8 GPa for E-glass to 121.5 GPa for AS4-graphite PPS as compared to 39.8 to 118.7 GPa for similar 40 ply composites. The compressive moduli of the composites are plotted as a function of E-glass PPS volume fraction in Figures 4 (a,b). The expected compressive moduli predicted by laminate theory using the experimentally measured compressive moduli for unidirectional AS4-graphite and E-glass PPS are also depicted in the Figure 3 a. The agreement between theory and experimental data is good for unidirectional composites.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Effect of Hybridization on Ultimate Compressive Properties Figures 3 (a,b) show the variation of experimental compressive strengths with E-glass PPS content 16 and 40 ply composites for the unidirectional composites along with the theoretical predictions. The maximum composite strength are seen for 75% AS4-graphite / 25% E-glass PPS composites. The failure strains of the composites also increase significantly on addition of E-glass PPS to the AS4-graphite PPS. The strengths are significantly higher than the predictions by iso-strain approach which assumes that composite fail at failure strain of low elongation component i.e. 100% AS4-graphite PPS. However from the experimental data, it is clear that the failure strain of the hybrid AS4-graphite / E-glass PPS composites is significantly higher than that of 100% AS4-graphite PPS composites. The hybridization by E glass thus provides for failure strain enhancement in the compressive mode. The failure strains of the composites is not solely controlled by 0° AS4-graphite reinforcement and thus the use of the iso-strain approach to calculate compressive strengths is incorrect. The agreement between the predictions by strain transfer approach and experiments is also not satisfactory. The strength of 75% AS4-graphite hybrid composites is higher than the predictions by strain transfer approach. The effect of residual stresses were found to be insignificant, less than 5% of failure strengths of the composites [15]. The experimentally obtained elastic moduli agree well with theoretical predictions for unidirectional composites for 16 and 40 thickness (Figure 4 a, b).

4.2 Hybrid Effect in Compressive Response of PPS laminates The compressive strength and strain results for AS4-graphite / E-glass hybrid composites indicate a very strong hybrid effect in compression. The hybrid enhancement can be defined as:

$$\text{HYE} = (\epsilon'_{\text{fail}} - \epsilon_{\text{fail}}) / \epsilon_{\text{fail}} \quad (5)$$

where ϵ'_{fail} is the experimental failure strain of hybrid composite and ϵ_{fail} is the failure strain of the 100% AS4-graphite composite of the particular orientation and thickness. The hybrid effects (HYE) calculated based on the above equation are listed in Table I and are average of more than four tests. The composites show hybrid effect of about 20% to 64%. The addition of weaker E-glass PPS on surface of stronger AS 4 graphite composite results in increase of compression strength. The large hybrid effects are related to the compressive failure modes of the composites. The AS4-graphite fibers in the composites fail by compressive buckling followed by kink band formation due to the low fiber / PPS matrix interfacial strength. In 100% AS4-graphite PPS composite, the buckling of fibers can easily initiate at the surface and rapidly propagate across the composite and result in the composite failure. In a hybrid composite, the highly loaded, high modulus AS4-graphite is shielded by the E-glass. Hence surface defect sites of the highly loaded graphite component are not available for unsupported

buckling of graphite fibers. The E-glass PPS on the surface also provides suitable transverse support to AS4-graphite. The E-glass fibers have a larger diameter and stronger fiber - PPS matrix interface bond than graphite-PPS interface. The higher failure strains of glass fibers allows them to undergo greater deformations before fracture as compared to graphite fibers. This allows E-glass fibers to arrest of the kink band propagation in highly loaded AS4-graphite region. These factors contribute to higher resistance to unsupported buckling of the graphite fibers. Thus the transverse support and crack arresting characteristics of E-glass combined with the elimination of surface defect sites available for initiation of buckling in AS4-graphite result in high hybrid effect observed in the compression testing.

4.3 Effect of Thickness on the Compressive properties The thickness of the AS4-graphite / E-glass PPS has a significant effect on the compressive properties. The failure strengths and strains are particularly low for the 16 ply composites, e.g. the 16 ply unidirectional AS4-graphite laminates failed at a strain of 0.34% as against 0.44% for the 40 ply composites. The unidirectional E-glass PPS composites also show lower compressive failure strain for 16 ply specimen - 0.69% for 16 ply and 1.27% for the 40 ply composites. The lower failure strains and stresses of 16 ply composites are attributed to the larger aspect ratios (l/d). The gage length of both 16 and 40 ply compression specimen was 25 mm. Thus the 16 ply composites tested had a aspect ratio of 10 versus 4 for the 40 ply specimen. Due to their high aspect ratio, Euler buckling plays a significant role in the failure of 16 ply composites. In reality the failure of thinner specimen is a result of combination of structural and micro-buckling which results in lower failure strains and strengths. The lower compressive response of the thin section composites is also due to the testing technique utilized. The end-loaded compression testing fixture designed is more suitable for testing thicker specimen. Thus a combination of test specimen geometry resulting in buckling of the specimen and the end loaded compression testing fixture lead to a lower strength of the 16 ply specimen. In addition to the iso-strain predictions, the critical buckling loads for the 16 ply composites are also plotted along with the experimental data in Figure 3 b. The predicted buckling loads increase rapidly with increasing AS4-graphite content. This is expected since equation 2 has bending modulus term which increases rapidly with higher fraction of high modulus AS4-graphite fibers. The strengths for hybrid composites are in a reasonable agreement with the predicted buckling loads. However, the predicted buckling load for the 100% AS4-graphite composites is significantly higher than the experimentally observed failure strengths. The lower buckling strength of the 16 ply graphite specimen is probably due to the lower fiber - matrix interfacial strength of AS 4 graphite PPS. This low interfacial strength and correspondingly premature fiber - matrix interfacial failure has an effect similar to that of delamination or longitudinal splitting, i.e. increasing the aspect ratio of unsupported AS4-graphite PPS fibers. The higher effective aspect ratio facilitates premature buckling of the 100% AS4 graphite composite .

4.4 Statistical Analysis of the Compressive Strengths The compressive response combines the effect of specimen aspect ratio, testing technique and geometry. The experimental compressive data showed some scatter about the mean. Table I presents the standard deviation of the compressive strength data for the different volume fractions of 16 and 40 ply thick composites respectively. To test the validity of data and the enhancement of the strength upon hybridization of AS4-graphite PPS composite, a statistical analysis of the compressive strength based on 'Student's t' distribution data was performed [16]. The 't' distribution is similar to the more widely used normal distribution. The results obtained from 't' distribution are useful for small populations versus normal distribution which can be used only for large population. The statistical significance of the difference between the mean strengths of 100% AS4-graphite and 75% AS4-graphite / E-glass composite was determined. By determining the 't' score for the difference between the means of the two different distributions, i.e., the data for 100% and 75% AS4-graphite reinforcement, a significance can be established. 't' score of 4.88 and 1.47 are obtained for the 16 and 40 ply unidirectional composite. This signifies a greater than 80 % confidence level about existence of a hybrid effect in these composites. A more extensive data base (i.e. greater than 25 specimens for each configuration) would be needed to determine the exact magnitudes of the strength enhancements.

4.5 Compressive Failure Analysis Macro and microscopic techniques were utilized to distinguish the failure modes in hybrid composites versus 100% AS4 graphite or E glass composites. The dominant fracture mode for compressive loaded specimen was kink band formation. Optical microscopy provided a useful tool to study the initiation of kink bands. Composite specimen loaded to about 80% of the failure stresses were observed by optical microscope to study the fracture initiation. Scanning electron microscopy provided useful

information on the fracture modes of individual fibers and the role of fiber-matrix interface on the fracture.

The optical micrographs in Figures 5 (a,b,c) depict the compressive failure in specimen loaded to stresses lower than fracture stresses. Figures 5 (a,b) show the difference between the failure of unidirectional AS4-graphite and E-glass PPS composites. The fracture is by kink band formation across the thickness of the specimen. Although both the fibers show bending, the graphite fibers exhibit greater fiber breakage than the glass fibers. The failure initiation in the hybrid composite, is in graphite PPS as seen in Figure 5 c. The adjacent glass PPS is relatively undamaged. Figure 6 (a,b) are hybrid composite failure macrographs of a unidirectional 50% AS4-graphite / 50% E-glass PPS composite. Figure 6 a shows the initiation of the fracture in the graphite region. The glass on the outside forced the kink band to form across the width of the specimen, and not across the thickness as in 100% AS4-graphite and E-glass PPS. Further loading of the specimen results in delamination and failure in glass (Figure 5 b). The differences between the failure characteristics of AS4-graphite, E-glass and the hybrid composites is illustrated schematically in Figure 7. The unidirectional AS4-graphite PPS and E-glass PPS fail by kink band formation across the thickness of the specimen, i.e. in the x-y plane as seen in Figure 7. The failure initiation is at the surface of the composite. Upon hybridization, E-glass PPS restrains the kink band formation in AS4-graphite across the thickness i.e. the x-z plane. Alternatively, the kink band is formed across the width of the specimen where the graphite is not restrained by glass. Scanning electron micrographs (Figures 8 a,b) shows evidence of micro-buckling of the individual fibers. The 16 ply composites (Figure 8 a) also show some fiber pullout, located on the tensile side of the structurally buckled composites. For comparison, Figure 8 b is the scanning electron micrographs of fractured graphite of 40 ply unidirectional 75% AS4 graphite / 25% E-glass hybrid composites. The failure shows no fiber pullout which indicates that failure was not by column buckling but by micro-buckling following debonding with the matrix. The tensile and compressive failure regions in the individual fibers can be distinguished and are marked T and C respectively.

In summary, it can be said that the failure of 16 ply specimen often occurs by structural buckling. However at a micro-level, the failure does not differ significantly from the 40 ply composite. The failure initiates by bending of exterior fibers and propagates by kink band formation. The graphite and glass PPS maintain their fracture characteristics in the 16 ply specimen. For thin samples Euler buckling is the primary failure mode and leads to lower failure strength of the composites.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The compression evaluation of 40 ply specimen utilized a newly designed end loaded fixture. Unlike the tensile response, the compressive properties show a great dependence on the thickness and the geometry of the test samples. Due to their large specimen aspect ratio ($l/d = 10$), Euler or structural buckling dominates the failure of 16 ply specimen. In contrast, thicker 40 ply specimens ($l/d = 4$) fail at significantly higher stresses and strains versus the 16 ply specimen. The use of iso-strain theory, which assumes that the hybrid composites to fail at the failure strains of unidirectional AS4-graphite is incorrect. Hence, a rule of mixture theory was used to predict the strength of hybrid composites. The compressive ultimate strengths of the hybrid composites were significantly higher than the theoretical predictions. The elastic moduli agreed with the theoretical predictions.

The hybrid effect observed in the compressive modes are much higher versus tension mode [16]. Compressive strain enhancements of 20 - 64% were observed for unidirectional hybrid composites. The maximum compressive strengths were obtained for 75% AS4-graphite / 25% E-glass PPS hybrid composites. It was postulated that the increased failure strains are due to transverse support by the more damage tolerant E-glass fibers. The glass fibers at the surface provides for higher failure strain and improved transverse strength which inhibits premature microbuckling failure. The fractography indicated that the failure mode in the 0° oriented plies was predominantly by kink band formation. For unidirectional composites, hybridization by E-glass rotates the plane of kink band propagation from the thickness direction to the width direction. The fracture behavior of 16 and 40 ply composites are similar at the microstructural level.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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TABLE I

Average Compressive Properties of 16 and 40 ply AS4-graphite / E-glass PPS Hybrid Unidirectional Composites

AS4-graphite/ E-glass	σ_{AV} (MPa)	σ_{dev}	E_{AV} (GPa)	e_{AV} (%)	HYE (%)	't' score
16 PLY						
1/0	346.1	8.5	121.5	0.34	-	4.8
3/1	420.7	29.4	107.8	0.44	29.41	
1/1	405.5	8.4	76.5	0.54	58.82	
1/3	382.0	21.8	68.0	0.53	55.88	
0/1	312.3	23.3	39.8	0.69	-	
40 PLY						
1/0	495.0	22.5	118.7	0.44	-	1.47
3/1	524.1	31.1	97.6	0.53	20.45	
1/1	499.0	25.7	71.3	0.61	38.63	
1/3	496.0	8.36	66.7	0.72	63.64	
0/1	456.0	22.2	39.8	1.14	-	

Figure 1 - Schematic of AS4 graphite - E glass PPS hybrid composite used for evaluating the compressive response of thick section hybrid composites

Figure 2 - (a) End loaded compression test fixture for thick section composites and (b) Compression test coupon

Figure 3 - Compressive failure strength (MPa) vs. volume fraction E-glass PPS for (a) 40 ply and (b) 16 ply thick hybrid composite specimen

Figure 4 - Compressive elastic moduli (GPa) vs. volume fraction E-glass PPS for (a) 40 ply and (b) 16 ply thick hybrid composite specimen

Figure 5 - Optical micrographs showing kink band formation in (a) AS4-graphite PPS, (b) E-glass PPS and (c) 50% AS4-graphite / E-glass PPS hybrid composite

Figure 6 - Compressive failure macrographs of 40 ply, 50% AS4-graphite / 50% E-glass PPS hybrid specimen showing, (a) failure initiation and (b) kink band propagation

Figure 7 - Schematic illustration of the failure modes of non - hybrid fiber composite and hybrid AS4-graphite / E glass PPS composite

(a)

(b)

Figure 8 - Scanning electron micrographs showing compressive failure surfaces of (a) 16 ply AS4-graphite PPS and (b) 40 ply AS4-graphite PPS composites.